

ASSESSMENT OF CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH ATRIAL FIBRILLATION

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Abstract. Atrial fibrillation (AF) leads among all arrhythmias in terms of severity of complications and adverse outcomes, and in terms of its prevalence in the population it is second only to extrasystole. The incidence of AF at a young age ranges from 0.4 to 1.0%, and in older age groups it increases to 8%. It has been established that COPD is an important risk factor for the development of hypertension, coronary artery disease, arrhythmias, heart failure, and sudden cardiac death. One of the leading reasons for the combination of COPD and cardiovascular diseases is the common risk factor - smoking, and a decrease in forced expiratory volume in 1 second (FEV1) is regarded as a predictor of the development of cardiovascular diseases and is associated with an increase in mortality.

The relationship between AF and COPD is not fully understood. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and AF share common risk factors that contribute to the occurrence of both diseases. In addition, COPD may also directly contribute to the occurrence of AF through the pathophysiological mechanisms associated with COPD. Correct diagnosis of COPD in patients with AF is important because COPD in patients with AF is a negative prognostic factor for the progression of paroxysmal AF to persistent AF and the effectiveness of AF treatment.

Keywords: COPD, FEV1, demographic, anthropometric and clinical-biochemical indicators.

Purpose of the study: to assess the clinical course of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease associated with atrial fibrillation.

Materials and methods: 80 patients with COPD were examined, of which 47 patients (group 1) with concomitant stable CHF I-III FC with AF, 43 patients (group 2) COPD without AF.

Patients with a verified diagnosis of COPD GOLD (2011) were examined and treated at RSMNPTs and MR. In the analyzed population, the frequency and structure of risk factors for the development and progression of AF were studied.

All COPD patients included in the study underwent standard 12-lead electrocardiography on a Schiller AT-2 plus electrocardiograph (Switzerland), followed by assessment of standard parameters. Ventilation function was assessed using a spirometer.

Drug therapy for patients with COPD was carried out taking into account a comprehensive assessment of COPD (frequency of exacerbations, spirometric data, severity of clinical symptoms).

The patients were divided into two groups: the first group of patients consisted of patients with COPD with the presence of atrial fibrillation.

The control group consisted of patients with COPD without AF, who were selected from patients with COPD who did not have a history of AF, and were matched to patients with COPD with AF by age and gender.

In addition, an analysis was carried out of the relationship between the frequency of risk factors and the number of exacerbations of COPD during the last year in patients with COPD with and without atrial fibrillation.

Continuous variables are presented as means and standard deviations and were compared between case and control groups using Student's t test. Discrete variables are presented as counts and percentages and were compared between the case and control groups using the chi-square test. P values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results of the study: analysis of anamnestic data demonstrated that the percentage of patients with type II diabetes mellitus was 18%, that is, 15 out of 80 patients. 68 patients were smokers, 68 patients received antihypertensive treatment. In 23 patients, a history of myocardial infarction and stroke was identified.

The main demographic, anthropometric and clinical-biochemical indicators are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Clinical parameters of patients with CHF based on the presence/absence of AF

Parameter	Patients with AF, n=80	Patients without AF, n=80	P
Age, years	64,2±0,45	54,6±10,7	<0,05
Women/Men	44(55%)/ 36 (45%)	52(65%)/ 28(35%)	<0,05
Duration of CHF (months)	19,7±5,6	16,7±4,6	>0,05
Hemoglobin, g/l	126,4±17,5	132,0±13,2	>0,05
Creatinine (μmol/l)	129,8±10,5	91,9±7,6	<0,05
SBP, mmHg	155,0±23,4	154,4±24,5	>0,05
DBP, mmHg	91,8±11,3	90,2±13,4	>0,05
Scale for assessing the clinical condition of a patient with CHF (point)	9,3±0,17	5,5±0,13	<0,05
6 minute walk test, m	282,6±48,7	367,4±39,2	>0,05

Among patients with CHF due to AF, the duration of the disease averaged 19.7±5.6 months, while in the group of patients with CHF it was 16.7±4.6 months, which did not have reliable values, but tended to earlier indicators of the manifestation of CHF.

Hemoglobin values, SBP and DBP data were not reliable across patient groups.

The results of the scale assessments had their significant differences, so significantly high scores on the SCS scale were established in patients with CHF against the background of AF: 9.3±0.17 versus 5.5±0.13 (P<0.05), which indicates the predominance in the group of patients without AF of CHF I and II FC, while the addition of AF aggravates the clinical symptoms of CHF, these patients correspond to III-IV FC.

The data obtained are also confirmed by the results of Doppler ultrasound of the carotid arteries in patients with COPD against the background of atrial fibrillation (Table 2).

Table 2

Dopplerography of the carotid arteries in patients with COPD and AF (n=80)

Parameter	Patients with COPD and AF, (n=80)
Intima media thickness, mm	0,65±0,14
Inner diameter, mm	6,6±0,8
Number of plaques, number	1,4±0,6

When conducting univariate analysis among factors, such indicators as age ($r = 0.76$, $P < 0.001$), male gender ($r = 0.46$, $P < 0.001$), systolic blood pressure ($r = 0.38$, $P < 0.001$), serum glucose ($r = 0.29$, $P = 0.01$), smoking ($r = 0.37$, $P = 0.002$) and previous history of acute myocardial infarction and acute cerebrovascular accident ($r=0.27$, $P=0.02$) showed a significant correlation with the severity of atherosclerotic lesions.

At the same time, a significant difference was revealed in the level of FEV1 ($p < 0.001$), FEV1 / FVC, % ($p = 0.030$), which were significantly lower in patients with AF (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Comparative analysis of respiratory function in the examined patients

A significantly low tolerance to physical activity was established in patients with COPD against the background of AF ($P < 0.01$). Thus, the Tiffno index in patients with AF was significantly lower and averaged $67.8 \pm 8.6\%$, while in patients without AF it increased on average to $71.8 \pm 11.2\%$ ($P < 0.01$).

In patients with COPD against the background of AF, exacerbations of this pathology were most often observed in relation to patients without AF (2.4 ± 0.03 versus 1.3 ± 0.02 times per year; $P < 0.05$).

Table 3

Content of biomarkers in patients with COPD and AF and in the comparison group.

Parameter	Control group (n=80)	Patients with COPD+AF (n=80)	P
IL-10, pg/ml	1,3 (0,6-3,4)	0,6 (0,6-2,4)	n/a
IL -6, pg/ml	0,7 (0,7-2,6)	1,6 (0,6-1,8)	<0.05
IL -8, pg/ml	7,4 (3,1-11,15)	0,6 (0,6-1,4)	<0.05
Φ HO- α , pg/ml	11,4±4,3	11,1±0,8	<0.05
CRP, mg/l	1,4±0,6	6,3±1,3	<0.05
Fibrinogen, g/l	2,5±0,8	4,36±1,2	<0.05

An independent relationship between the biomarkers IL-6 and IL-8 and the severity of atherosclerotic lesions was identified using a multiple linear regression model adjusted for age, gender, smoking, history of AMI and stroke, SBP and blood glucose.

It was found that in patients with COPD and AF there is a 4.5-fold increase in CRP, which also indicates the development of the inflammatory process ($P < 0.01$).

It should be noted that IL-6 was the most significant biomarker, increasing the value of multiple R2 in the base model ($P < 0.05$) by 1.5 times than other biomarkers, having a significant predictor of atherosclerosis.

Discussion. Among the various parameters characterizing the remodeling of the walls of the carotid arteries and the development of atherosclerotic plaques in patients with CKD, only such an indicator as IL-6 showed a significant correlation not only with ultrasonographic indicators of the carotid arteries, but also achieved independent predictive power in a multifactorial model of the severity of atherosclerosis. IL-6, which is a potent mediator of inflammation, was the only biomarker that had a significant predictive role in an expanded model for predicting the severity of atherosclerosis. Similar conclusions were also obtained in a cohort study conducted in 1984–2002 [14]. A study devoted to predicting the risk of developing cardiovascular events in dialysis patients also demonstrated that IL-6 is a powerful mediator of inflammation, which has a significant prognostic role in the development of cardiovascular complications in patients with dialysis stages of CKD [7, 8, 9, 10]. Probably, the key role of IL-6 is associated with its ability to regulate the expression of other pro-inflammatory mediators, such as E-selectin, ICAM-1, VCAM-1, CRP [10, 11, 12, 13].

Adeloye et al. (2015) discussed the prevalence of COPD in their regional meta-analysis. At the same time, a high incidence of atrial fibrillation was revealed in patients with COPD,

Aldhoon et al. (2010) described the pathogenetic mechanisms of atrial fibrillation in patients with comorbid pathology. As in our study, the authors recognized the key role of ectopic foci in the pulmonary veins as a trigger of atrial fibrillation. Structural remodeling has been identified as a major mechanism of persistence of atrial fibrillation, supporting the predominant role of atrial fibrosis. Systemic inflammatory state, oxidative stress, autonomic balance, and neurohormonal activation have been identified as important modifiers influencing susceptibility to AF. New understanding of the pathophysiology of atrial fibrillation has led to the emergence of new treatment options. Ablation interventions, blockade of the renin-angiotensin system, modulation of oxidative stress and control of tissue fibrosis represent new approaches in the treatment of AF. The purpose of this review is to provide a concise overview of new insights into the mechanisms of AF and subsequent therapeutic strategies.

Alves Guimaraes et al. (2018) concluded that the Portuguese Acute Coronary Syndrome Registry found that a large percentage of patients with acute coronary syndrome had concomitant COPD. Andreas et al. (2005) described the pathogenetic mechanisms of neurohormonal disorders in patients with COPD and their significance in the prognosis of the disease. Our study also confirmed the pathogenetic mechanisms of the influence of neurohormonal disorders on the outcomes of patients with atrial fibrillation against the background of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

Thus, the results obtained demonstrated a significant correlation between some parameters of ultrasonography of the carotid arteries with markers of the development of atherosclerosis. At the same time, a study of markers responsible for pro-inflammatory, anti-inflammatory, metabolic effects in the body showed that indicators such as IL-6, CRP, fibrinogen showed a significant correlation with the severity of atherosclerosis in patients with COPD with AF. However, it is clear that longer-term studies will show the significance of these parameters.

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